

IMPACT OF MARKETING TECHNIQUES ON SALE OF FRESH FRUITS AND VEGETABLES - A STUDY

Prof. Sumathi C

Research Scholar in Bharathidasan University and Professor in Commerce, Seshadripuram
Commerce College, Magadi Road, Bengaluru.

Dr. K. Mala

Research Supervisor, Guest Lecturer in Commerce, Government Arts and Science
College, Thirumayam.

ABSTRACT

The importance of food is that it gives important nutrients and proteins. Some types of food give major proteins to the body that make the development of the structure of the body. The aim is to examine the situation of marketing performance of fresh fruits and vegetables in the market and the operational development of the market by the use of a mobile application. The brief description of impact and the concept of adapting technologies in the making of the development of marketing strategies of the fruits and vegetables market of India. In the methodology section, the study collects information from the primary sources of data collection. The participants at random selection have been surveyed with the help of Google form and number was taken as 55. The software known as SPSS is used to run the related testing of hypothesis and demographics. The primary survey has been conducted to get appropriate information from different sources and increases the information about the marketing adaptation of the fruit and vegetable market. It discusses all the statistical analysis of the collected data from the people of the country. The implementation of mobile applications in the performance of the producers is adhered with examination of customer expectations and delivery of the best output to them in the required quantity and quality. Therefore it discusses all examination procedures and the application impact of the marketing technique in the vegetable and fruit market providing fresh fruit and vegetable that improve the health condition of the People including the people of Bangalore. It concludes all the making of all the analysis of the development of the structure of the body. The consumption of fresh fruits provides many nutrients and proteins to the body. So people depend on and find fresh from the market to get more effective development in the body by the consumption of fruits.

Keywords: Fresh fruits and Vegetables, marketing, Management strategies, adaptation of technologies, marketing factors

INTRODUCTION

In the making of the development of health conditions fruits and vegetables work as the important and primary factor. The importance of food is that it gives important nutrients and proteins. Some types of foods give major proteins to the body that make the development of the structure of the body.

Figure 1:Regions of the fruit producing States in the India

(Source: Umarov et al. 2019)

The consumption of fresh fruit provides many nutrients and proteins to the body. So, people depend on and find fresh from the market to get more effective development in the body by the consumption of fruit (Umarov et al. 2019). Figure 1 makes the description of the places where the production takes place and the major part is covered by Bangladesh and other countries.

Figure 2: Growing issues in the fruits and vegetable market of India

(Source: Statista, 2023)

In the marketing of fruits and vegetables, the quality of the fruits and vegetables increases the demand for them in the market. The above-shown figure 2 shows the changes in the marketing demand of fruits and vegetables and it can be seen that there is an increasing trend in the overall production process. This includes the increases of demand more from the year 2019 to 2022 (Statista, 2023). This especially changed due to the increase of the Covid pandemic situations.

Aim: The study aims to examine the situation of marketing performance of fresh fruits and vegetables in the market and the operational development of the market by the use of a mobile application.

The following are the objectives of the study

- To state the concept of fresh fruit and vegetables marketing
- To elaborate on the impact of the digital medium application in the marketing performance of fruits and vegetables
- To identify some of the issues generated in the development of fruit and vegetable marketing
- To describe some of the mitigating methods improving the marketing factor for increasing the demand of the market

The following are the question that the study elaborates

- What is the significance of using digital media applications in marketing tactics?
- How to examine the marketing performance of vegetables and fruits?
- What are the impacts of marketing adaptation?
- What are the benefits of the mobile application in marketing performances on humans?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of fruits and vegetable Operational marketing strategy

The making of development in the physical and mental conditions of humans the consumption of nutrient rich food is much essential. That includes the consumption of fresh vegetables and fruits. It makes some of the implementations of the factor in the circulation of blood in the body. As per the opinions of Mkhize & Ellis (2020), the attraction of customers to the market depends on the quality and the affordable price of the product in the market. The competitive advantages in the marketing performances make the development of the producers among the other competitors in the market.

Figure 3: Concept of fruits and vegetable Operational marketing strategy

(Source: Influenced by Umarov et al.2019)

The best products in the market fulfill the expectation and the demand of the market in quantity and quality becomes the top performer in the market as shown in figure 3. It also includes the implementation of some of the strategies and planning for increasing the influence of marketing performance by the suppliers.

Impact of mobile applications in developing the marketing performance of Vendors

In the making of the development in the market of fruit and vegetables producers make adaptations of some of the strategies in the making of the development. They make regular examinations of the expectations and the demands of the customers in the market. In the perspective of the consumers of the vegetable and fruit market, they focus on getting the best quality of the fruit from the market. That implements nutrients to their body. The customers get the best knowledge about the factor and the quality of the food for different purposes. Fresh foods act as the key factor in providing nutrients, proteins, and vitamins to the body. Based on the views of Umarov et al. (2019) the importance of consuming fresh foods is very necessary in the making of health development. By relating to the performance of the producers to the consumers the best supplier of fresh and qualified fruit and vegetables becomes one of the preferable choices of the market. That includes the implementation of mobile applications in the performance of the producers by the examination of customer expectations and delivery of the best output to them in the required quantity and quality.

Theory

Business process redesigning

Figure 4: Business process redesigning

(Source: Influenced by Kumari & John 2019)

The above figure has mentioned the five different stages of restructuring of the business structure. It denotes the basic development in the operational performances of business authority. The theory makes the development of the function of the business by implementing some of the factors that make the development of marketing performance (Grewal et al 2019). It actually refers to recreating the system of the business operation for the development of the business through the application some of the implementation in the marketing operation of the vendors. This theory also states the developmental activities of society and the impact of the product on the satisfaction level of the customers (Kumari & John 2019). On the other hand, arguments products denote the products have issues in quality. This theory has described the systematic ways to increase demand of the market.

Methodology

In the methodology section, the study collects information from the primary sources of data collection. The primary survey has been conducted to get appropriate information from different sources and increases the information about the marketing adaptation of the fruit and vegetable market. According to the views of Perez-Ferrer et al. (2019), a primary survey includes questions and it helps to collect fresh data from the respondents. This increases the quality of data as well as develops the level of preciseness of the research work. Based on the views of Massaglia et al. (2019), primary data has supported by quantitative analysis and it includes various statistical calculations. This increases the overall quality of the task as it is based on scientific processes. The researcher has followed all the different steps of the research sequentially. The 55 numbers of respondents attended the survey and the SPSS tool has been used for the validation of the surveyed result.

Finding and analysis

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis 1

H1: Operational marketing depends on the marketing strategy of the business authority

H0: Operational marketing does not depend on the marketing strategy of the business authority

Hypothesis 2

H1: Marketing adaptation makes the development of the marketing operations

H0: Marketing adaptation does not make the development of the marketing operations

Hypothesis 3

H1: The application of digital mediums makes the development of the operational task of marketing

H0: The application of digital mediums does not make the development of the operational task of marketing

Demographic data

Age

2. What is your age?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Above 55	5	9.1	9.1	9.1
	Between 20 to 35	10	18.2	18.2	27.3
	Between 36 to 45	5	9.1	9.1	36.4
	Between 46 to 55	35	63.6	63.6	100.0
	Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Table 1: Age analysis

(Source: SPSS)

The respondents between the age of 20 to 35 are 18.18% and others two age groups are 9.09% each as can be seen in table 1.

Figure 5: Age analysis

(Source: SPSS)

The age group of responders reflects their own view on the marketing performance in the market (Han et al.2021). Figure 5 describes the maximum percentage of respondents is belonging from the age of 46 to 55 as 63.64% of them are in this group of age as they know about the market in detail.

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Female	15	27.3	27.3	27.3
Male	25	45.5	45.5	72.7
Prefer not to say	15	27.3	27.3	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Gender analysis

(Source: SPSS)

Figure 6: Gender analysis

(Source: SPSS)

This reflects the perspective differences among the genders of the society on the topic of the study (Boiko et al.2019). Table 2 and figure 6 shows that there is 45.45% are male respondents and the female respondents are 27.27% other 27.27% of respondents prefers not to say their gender.

Monthly income

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Above Rs 50000	5	9.1	9.1	9.1
Below Rs 45000	5	9.1	9.1	18.2
Between Rs 30000 to 50000	35	63.6	63.6	81.8
Between Rs 45000 to 30000	10	18.2	18.2	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Analysis of monthly income

(Source: SPSS)

Figure 7: Analysis of income

(Source: SPSS)

63.64% of respondents have income between 30000 and 50000, 9.09 % of respondents have income above 50000 and below 10000 and 30000 to 45000 are 18.18% each among the respondents as can be seen in table 3 and figure 7. This all reflects the income status of the responders. The opinions change as per their perspective of them about the topic of the study (Kim & Adhikari, 2020).

Descriptive analysis

Hypothesis 1

Model Summary ^a										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.890 ^a	.793	.789	.99087	.793	202.557	1	53	.000	1.635

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	198.873	1	198.873	202.557	.000 ^b
	Residual	52.036	53	.982		
	Total	250.909	54			

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.061	.420		2.526	.015
	IV1	.599	.042	.890	14.232	.000

Table 4: Hypothesis 1

(Source: SPSS)

The above table 4 has shown the calculation and the values of regression analysis of hypothesis 1. The significance value of this regression analysis is 0.000. The significance value of regression below 0.005 denotes the close relationship between them. The R square value is 0.793 which is significant. Including that the r value is .890 this all indicates that the analysis is significant in providing all the necessary information of the study.

Hypothesis 2

Model Summary ^a										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.860 ^a	.740	.735	1.11033	.740	150.523	1	53	.000	2.022

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	185.569	1	185.569	150.523	.000 ^b
	Residual	65.340	53	1.233		
	Total	250.909	54			

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.864	.424		4.399	.000
	IV2	.469	.038	.860	12.269	.000

Table 5: Hypothesis 2

(Source: SPSS)

The above table 5 has shown the calculation and the values of regression analysis of hypothesis 2. The significance value of this regression analysis is 0.000. The significance value of regression below 0.005 denotes the close relationship between them. The R square value is 0.860 which is significant. Including that the r value is .740 this all indicates that the analysis is significant in providing all the necessary information of the study.

Hypothesis 3

Model Summary ^a										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.863 ^a	.745	.740	1.09876	.745	154.830	1	53	.000	2.400

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	186.923	1	186.923	154.830	.000 ^b
Residual	63.986	53	1.207		
Total	250.909	54			

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.881	.417		4.514	.000
	IV3	.692	.056	.863	12.443	.000

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	3.2657	8.8042	6.7273	1.86052	55
Residual	-1.26573	1.96503	.00000	1.08854	55
Std. Predicted Value	-1.861	1.116	.000	1.000	55
Std. Residual	-1.152	1.788	.000	.991	55

Table 6: Hypothesis 3

(Source: SPSS)

The above table 6 has shown the calculation and the values of the regression analysis of hypothesis 3. The significance value of this regression analysis is 0.000. The significance value of regression below 0.005 denotes the close relationship between them. The R square value is 0.745 which is significant. Including that the r value is .863 this all indicates that the analysis is significant in providing all the necessary information of the study.

DISCUSSION

The study analyzes the development that occurred in the adaption of new methodological techniques. This includes the making of management strategical adaptation of the marketing performances of the business authority. Primary data has supported by quantitative analysis and it includes various statistical calculations (Massaglia et al.2019). This increases the overall quality of the task as it is based on scientific processes. The researcher has followed all the different steps of the research sequentially. 55 numbers of respondents attended the survey and the SPSS tool has been used for the validation of the surveyed result (Mkhize & Ellis, 2020). This collection of the data is then analysed by the statistical analysis software SPSS. The making development helps in examining the effect of adapted management technologies in the marketing operation of the business authority.

It includes all the importance of consuming fresh foods is very necessary in the making of health development. By relating to the performance of the producers to the consumers the best supplier of fresh and qualified fruit and vegetables becomes one of the preferable choices of the market (Kumari, & John 2019). That includes the implementation of mobile

applications in the performance of the producers by the examination of customer expectations and delivery of the best output to them in the required quantity and quality. Therefore it discusses all examination procedures and the application impact of the marketing technique in the vegetable and fruit market providing fresh fruit and vegetable that improve the health condition of the People including the people of Bangalore.

CONCLUSION

It concludes all the making of all the analysis of the development of the structure of the body. The consumption of fresh fruit provides many nutrients and proteins to the body. So people depend on and find fresh from the market to get more effective development in the body by the consumption of fruit. The study makes the collection of information from the primary sources of the data collection. That reflects the recent condition of the marketing performances of the operational development in the fruit and vegetable market. It analyses all the factors that are used in the making of the marketing development. It also suggests some of the strategies that make the development of the producers in the market to attract more customers increasing the revenue generation.

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